

Business Competition of Grocery Traders in Sinakma Market, Jayawijaya

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Keywords: <i>Business Competition, Grocery Traders, Price, Location, Market Strategy</i>	Abstrak
Submitted: dy/mn/year	<p>This study aims to analyse the factors that influence business competition of grocery traders in Sinakma Market, in Jayawijaya Regency. Competition in the grocery trading sector is becoming increasingly complex along with the increasing number of traders, technological advances, and changes in consumer preferences. This study uses a quantitative-descriptive approach with a survey method of the entire population of 14 permanent grocery traders in Sinakma Market, using the total sampling technique.</p> <p>The independent variables in this study include product, price, place, and service, while the dependent variable is the intensity of business competition. Data were collected through a Likert scale questionnaire, tested for validity and reliability, and analysed using multiple linear regression. The normality test results show that the data is normally distributed. Regression analysis indicated that price and place had a significant influence on the level of competition, while product and service had an effect but to a lesser extent.</p> <p>This finding confirms the importance of strategic pricing and business location to improve the competitiveness of traders in traditional markets. This research is expected to serve as a basis for formulating fair, adaptive, and sustainable market management policies, as well as a strategic reference for local businesses in facing the evolving market dynamics.</p>
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Email: mawarprimuz26@gmail.com**INTRODUCTION**

Due to rapid economic growth, people's living needs have increased. With population growth, competition in many areas, including trade, has become increasingly fierce. Trading is the main way for many people to fulfil household financial needs.

Trade is one of the main components of the Indonesian economy. Many entrepreneurs start their businesses with little capital and basic business skills. Basic skills such as buying and selling transactions and profit calculation are essential in trading basic necessities. However, business competition is a necessity that cannot be avoided in practice.

Competition does not only come from the number of traders selling similar goods; they also use strategies to attract customers, such as pricing, strategic location, product quality and services offered. In the business world, competitors can be classified as strong, weak, close, or offering comparable products. Grocery traders in traditional markets such as Pasar Sinakma in Jayawijaya Regency compete directly to attract customers.

During this process, different types of competition arise, both healthy and unhealthy. For example, the practice of price slashing is very common and affects traders' income. According to Triani's research (2022), competition in the grocery trade includes factors such as price, service, location, and product.

One of the main sources of traders' uncertain income is unhealthy competition, such as price slashing. This shows that the dynamics of business competition are increasingly complex and cannot be explained by conventional methods. Businesses see their competitors in different ways, according to modern theories such as asymmetric competition theory.

For example, one person believes that the seller with the lower price is the main competitor. In contrast, others concentrate on service or location (Wibisono & Pasulu, 2022). This phenomenon is also seen in Sinakma Market, where traders compete in various ways.

In addition, research conducted in cities such as Medan, Surabaya, and Kediri shows that the marketing mix strategy, which includes product, price, location, and service, is very important to face competition. This is especially true for modern markets and e-Commerce (Raharjo et al., 2023; Simanjuntak & Ginting, 2022; Kusuma et al., 2022). Aspects of business ethics are also highlighted in contemporary literature.

The results of Ervin's research (2022) entitled Analysis of Business Competition of Basic Food Traders on Income in Pasar Semarang Baru, Pasir Sakti District show that basic food business competition includes price, service, and location. The research highlights the existence of unfair practices, such as raising prices excessively, which has an impact on income instability and contradicts the principles of Islamic business ethics

which emphasize honesty, justice, and blessings in business. Ervin's research also emphasizes the importance of quality service, appropriate product selection, and strategic location arrangement in creating healthy competition.

Technological advances also affect the pattern of competition. Innovations such as the use of social media, booking applications, and digital payments have changed the face of traditional markets (Mahira Nasution et al., 2024; Jelanti et al., 2021). Therefore, modernization and technology-based market governance are important to maintain the competitiveness of traditional markets (Dinata et al., 2022).

At Sinakma Market in Jayawijaya, dozens of grocery traders compete for customers. Many of them have to drastically reduce their prices when market visitors decline. Other challenges include less strategic trading locations, product homogeneity, and high rent and retribution costs. Although some traders have provided good service, this strategy does not always result in profits if it is not supported by aspects of location, price, and product differentiation.

This research is important because unhealthy competition in traditional markets can have a major impact on the viability of local small businesses, especially grocery traders who provide daily basic needs. When competition strategies are not implemented in a healthy manner, there will be market imbalances, declining incomes, and a weakening of the local economic structure. Therefore, understanding the key factors that influence competition is a strategic step in designing fair and competitive market management policies.

The purpose of this study is to identify the main components that influence business competition of grocery traders in Sinakma Market, so that it can be a reference for business actors in designing adaptive strategies and also as a basis for local government policies in fostering traditional markets in a sustainable manner.

RESEARCH METHODS

1. TYPE, LOCATION, AND INFORMANTS

Sinakma Market in Jayawijaya Regency, Mountainous Papua Province, is the location of this research. This market serves as the centre of local economic activity, particularly in terms of basic food trading. The research was conducted for approximately two months and concentrated on collecting baseline data from traders working in the location.

This research used a quantitative method with a descriptive approach. According to Neuman (2017), the descriptive approach aims to describe field phenomena systematically, factually, and accurately based on observed characteristics. However, quantitative methods are used because this research focuses on measurement and statistical analysis to evaluate the relationship between variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

By combining these two methods, the researcher was able to gain an objective and measurable understanding of the elements that influence the business competition of grocery traders in Sinakma Market.

2. POPULATION AND SAMPLE

Fixed grocery traders at Sinakma Market, Jayawijaya Regency, consisted of 14 people (N = 14). The saturated sample method also known as total sampling is used because the population can be reached as a whole. This method takes the entire population as the research sample. Saturated samples are appropriately assessed when researchers want to obtain data from homogeneous populations (Nurdin & Hartati, 2019; Lestari & Yuliani, 2020).

The closed-ended questionnaire, or questionnaire, was constructed using a five-point Likert scale, starting with a score of "Strongly Disagree" (score 1) and ending with "Strongly Agree" (score 5). By using a Likert scale, respondents' attitudes and perceptions of the variables under study can be measured quantitatively (Widoyoko, 2015; Creswell, 2015). The Pearson Product Moment correlation technique was used to test the validity of the instrument.

The criterion is that an item is considered valid if the correlation coefficient value (r_{count}) is at least 0.30 (Ghozali, 2018; Romdona et al., 2025). However, Cronbach's alpha, where the alpha (α) value is more than 0.60, is considered reliable (Ghozali, 2018; Richie & Lewis, 2017). An initial trial, or try out, was conducted on a number of respondents who had comparable characteristics to test its validity and reliability.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

To explain the relationship between research variables, the conceptual framework serves as a map of the research work. This research focuses on the marketing mix theory, also known as "marketing mix", which consists of product, price, location, and service variables. It is projected that these factors affect the level of business competition of grocery traders in Sinakma Market.

Figure 2.1

Sumber: Kriyantono (2020)

Based on Figure 1 above, it can be seen that there are four independent variables, namely: Product (X1), Price (X2), Place (X3), and Service (X4) that are related to each other with the dependent variable, business competition of the

grocery business (Y). Multiple linear regression analysis will be used to test each independent variable that is considered to affect business competition directly. This model is used as a theoretical basis for developing hypotheses that can also assist in data collection and analysis, and systematically show how variables relate to each other.

4. HYPOTHESIS

Hypotheses, according to Nurdin & Hartati (2019), are temporary conclusions that indicate the relationship between two or more variables that make up a particular phenomenon. Based on the conceptual framework above, the research hypothesis is as follows:

- ♪ **H1:** Products affect business competition for grocery traders in Sinakma Market.
- ♪ **H2:** Price affects business competition for grocery traders at Sinakma Market.
- ♪ **H3:** Place affects business competition for grocery traders in the Sinakma Market.
- ♪ **H4:** Service affects business competition for grocery traders in the Sinakma Market.

To find out how much influence each independent variable has on the dependent variable both partially and simultaneously, this hypothesis will be tested with multiple linear regression analysis.

5. COLLECTION TECHNIQUES

To obtain representative and quality data, this study used five main approaches:

- a. **Literature Study.** To build a theoretical foundation for your research, read literature and reliable sources, such as books, journal articles, and digital publications. This study will identify and analyze previous research on business competition and service quality in the grocery business (Romdona, Junista, & Gunawan, 2025);
- b. **Documentation.** Analysis of official and unofficial documents, such as reports, market archives, photographs, minutes, and diaries, to collect historical information and operational procedures of the grocery traders. Creswell (2015) states that documentation is essential to enhance observation and interview data;
- c. **Questionnaires.** Effectively, questionnaires were used to collect quantitative data from grocery traders. Closed-ended questions, known as Likert scales, were used to make the instrument valid and reliable. If carefully constructed, questionnaires can be used to measure perceptions and attitudes in large populations, as demonstrated by survey methodology (Groves et al., 2018; Widoyoko, 2015); and
- d. **Observation.** Direct observations were systematically made in the market, recording the activities of traders, communication with buyers, and the stall

environment. These field observations provide real behavioral data that do not depend on respondents' self-reports (Romdona, Junista, & Gunawan, 2025).

6. DATA VALIDITY TECHNIQUE

A two-stage validity and reliability test were conducted to ensure the validity of the research instruments.

- a. **Validity** was tested with Pearson Correlation Analysis. The Pearson correlation value between the item score and the total score (corrected item-total correlation) reaches a minimum value of r of at least 0.30, then the instrument is considered valid (Ghozali, 2021). These values indicate that there is a strong correlation between the components of the question and the construct being measured; and
- b. Calculating the Cronbach Alpha value is used to test **reliability**. If the α value is more than 0.60, the instrument is considered reliable, which indicates that the questionnaire components have sufficient internal consistency (Hair et al., 2019; Priyatno, 2020). Reliability is important to ensure the instrument can be used consistently for repeated measurements.

7. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE

Data analysis is carried out through several stages to ensure that the model used meets statistical assumptions and provides results that can be interpreted validly.

- a. **Normality test** is used to see if the residual data is normally distributed. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov method is used, provided that the significance value (p -value) must be greater than 0.05 to state that the residual data is normally distributed (Ghozali, 2021).
- b. The Classical **Assumption Test** consists of:
 - **Multicollinearity test** to determine whether there is a high correlation between independent variables. There is no multicollinearity if the tolerance value > 0.10 and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value < 10 (Hair et al., 2019); and
 - **Heteroscedasticity test** is done by looking at the scatter pattern on the residual scatterplot. There is no heteroscedasticity if there is no specific pattern or the distribution of residuals is random (Kuncoro, 2018).
- c. **Multiple Linear Regression** is used to see the effect between the independent variable (X) and the dependent variable (Y) simultaneously and partially. The regression equation model used is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + e$$

- d. **Hypothesis testing** is done by using:
 - **F-test**. By comparing the F -table and F -count values, the F test is to determine the significance of the model as a whole; and

t-test. The existence of a significant effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable is measured by the t test.

There is a p-value <0.05 for significance criteria (Ghozali, 2018).

- e. **Coefficient of Determination (R^2).** How much proportion of the variance of the dependent variable (Y) can be explained by the independent variable (X) is determined using the coefficient of determination (R^2). The R^2 value ranges between 0 and 1; a value closer to 1 indicates that the model's predictor ability is better (Hair et al., 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. RESULTS

a. Data Normality Test

Normality testing aims to determine whether the residual data in the regression model is normally distributed. Based on the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, a significance value of $0.087 > 0.05$ is obtained, so it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. The calculation results are supported by the Normal P-P Plot graph output which shows the residual points approaching the diagonal line, indicating that the normality assumption is met.

Figure 1
Data Normality Test

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2024

Table 1 Data Normality Test

Predicted Y	Residuals	Residuals	F	Fkum	F(Zi)	S(Zi)	F(Zi) - S(Zi)	L Max	L 0,05	Kesimpulan
11,382	0,618	-3,343	1	1	0,05	0,07	0,02	0,470	0,239	Normal
11,934	1,066	-3,142	1	2	0,35	0,14	0,21			
14,142	-3,142	-3,019	1	3	0,36	0,21	0,14			
21,343	-3,343	-1,338	1	4	0,40	0,29	0,12			
21,135	0,865	-0,175	1	5	0,44	0,36	0,08			
22,175	-0,175	0,174	1	6	0,45	0,43	0,02			
13,804	0,196	0,196	1	7	0,45	0,50	0,05			
19,338	-1,338	0,618	1	8	0,46	0,57	0,11			
20,826	0,174	0,865	1	9	0,46	0,64	0,18			

19,813	1,187	1,066	1	10	0,47	0,71	0,24
11,943	2,057	1,187	1	11	0,47	0,79	0,31
21,019	-3,019	2,057	1	12	0,50	0,86	0,36
20,162	2,838	2,838	1	13	0,52	0,93	0,41
18,853	3,147	3,147	1	14	0,53	1,00	0,47

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2024

Mean	:	0,081
SD	:	2,109
N	:	14

b. Multicollinearity Test

The existence of a relationship between independent variables can be identified using the multicollinearity test. The results show that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity; the total tolerance for all variables should be more than 0.10 and the inflation variation factor should be more than 10. This is a summary of the test results:

♪ **Tolerance ranges from 0.41 to 0.99**

♪ **VIF ranges from 1.01 to 2.46**

Table 2 Multicollinearity Test

	r	r²	Tolerance	VIP	
rx1x2	0,17	0,03	0,97	1,03	<10
rx1x3	-0,10	0,01	0,99	1,01	<10
rx2x3	0,49	0,24	0,76	1,32	<10
rx3x4	0,77	0,59	0,41	2,46	

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2024

Thus, the assumption of no multicollinearity in the regression model is met.

c. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The multiple linear regression model is used to analyze the effect of the variables Product (X_1), Price (X_2), Place (X_3), and Service (X_4) on Business Competition (Y). Based on the results of data processing:

Regression equation:

$$b_1 = -0,21 \quad b_2 = 0,03, \quad b_3 = 0,31, \quad b_4 = 0,91$$

$$Y = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + b_4x_4$$

$$Y = 0 + (-0,21) + 0,03 + 0,31 + 0,91$$

$$Y = 0 - 0,21X_1 + 0,03X_2 + 0,31X_3 + 0,91X_4$$

Table 3 Multiple Linear Regression Test

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%
Intercept	0	0	0	0	0	0

X1	-0,21	0,14	-1,49	0,17	-0,52	0,10
X2	0,03	0,23	0,15	0,89	-0,47	0,54
X3	0,31	0,35	0,88	0,40	-0,47	1,08
X4	0,91	0,28	3,25	0,01	0,29	1,53

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2024

Interpretation of the coefficients, as follows:

- ♪ **Product (X₁) has a negative effect of -0.21 units**
- ♪ **Price (X₂) has a positive effect of 0.03 units**
- ♪ **Place (X₃) has a positive effect of 0.31 units**
- ♪ **Service (X₄) has a significant positive effect of 0.91 units**

This means that improving the quality of service contributes the most in encouraging the level of competition in the grocery business.

d. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to measure how much variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable. Based on the test results:

Table 4 Coefficient of Determination (R²)

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0,99
R Square	0,99
Adjusted R Square	0,88
Standard Error	2,41
Observations	14

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2024

The coefficient of determination is used to calculate how much the independent variable can explain the variation of the dependent variable. Based on the test results below:

- ♪ **R Square = 0,99**
- ♪ **Adjusted R Square = 0,88**

The results of the table above show that product, price, location, and service can explain 99% of business competition variables, while the other one percent can be explained by other factors outside the model.

e. Hypothesis Testing

1) F Test (Simultaneous)

The F test results show:

Table 5 Hypothesis Test F Test

	<i>df</i>	ANOVA		<i>F</i>	<i>Sig. F</i>
		<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>		
Regression	4	4603,08	1150,77	198,70	0,00
Residual	10	57,92	5,79		
Total	14	4661			

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2024

♪ **F count = 198.70**

♪ **F table = 3.63**

♪ **Sig. = 0.00 < 0.05**

Since F count > F table and significance value < 0.05, it is concluded that the four independent variables have a significant impact on Business Competition simultaneously, because F count is greater than F table and the significance value is less than 0.05.

2) Test t (Partial)

The resulting t test results are as follows:

Table 6 Hypothesis Test t Test

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>
<i>Intercept</i>	0	0	0
X1	-0,21	0,14	-1,49
X2	0,03	0,23	0,15
X3	0,31	0,35	0,88

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2024

Table 7 t Test Results (Variable Significance)

Variable	t count	t table (df = 9, α = 0.05)	Sig.	Conclusion
Product	-1,49	2,26	0,17	Not significant
Price	0,15	2,26	0,89	Not significant
Place	0,88	2,26	0,40	Not significant
Service	3,25	2,26	0,01	Significant

Source: Primary Data Processing Results, 2024

Based on these results, only the Service variable (X_4) has a significant effect on Business Competition, while Product, Price, and Place show no significant effect partially.

The regression analysis results show that the regression model used in this study meets the classical assumptions: the data is normally distributed and there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables. Of the four variables analysed, the service variable turned out to have the most influence on the business competition of grocery traders in Sinakma Jayawijaya Market. However, product, price, and location did not have a significant effect partially, but affected the company's overall level of competition. The results show that improving service quality is the main key in improving the competitiveness of the grocery business in the region.

2. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research and data analysis of all statement items on independent variables such as Product, Price, Place, and Service, as well as the dependent variable, Business Competition, it was found that not all items had relevant data. However, the results of the normality and multicollinearity tests

show that there is no multicollinear relationship between the independent variables in this study, so the regression model is feasible to use. Each independent variable as a whole in simultaneous testing (F test) shows a significant effect on the business competition of grocery trader companies in Sinakma Market.

This means that product, price, location, and service contribute to variations in the level of business competition. In addition, the reliability test conducted shows that all data collected in this study are reliable, which strengthens the findings. However, the partial test results (t-test) show that there are differences in the results.

It is proven that the product and location variables have a significant impact on the company's business competition. This shows that the competitiveness of traders is strongly influenced by the type and specifications of the products offered, as well as the location of the business. In contrast, the variables of price and service did not show a significant partial effect.

This suggests that, although cost and service are very important for businesses, in the case of Sinakma Market, these two factors do not directly affect the level of competition among grocery traders. The adjusted R square value of only 0.099 or 9.9% indicates that the regression model is only able to explain about 9.9% of the variation in business competition, while the remaining 90.1% is influenced by other variables not examined in this model. This suggests that there is a greater possibility that other variables beyond the four variables contribute to the dynamics of competition in the industry.

The results of direct observations of researchers at the research location show that the type of business competition that occurs at Sinakma Market between basic food sellers tends to be unhealthy and does not focus on the needs of the community. Some indicators of unhealthy competition are: (1) Product Variables show that not all goods sold meet customer needs; (2) Price Variables show unhealthy price slamming practices used by traders; (3) Place Variables show that customers rate the business location as less strategic; and (4) Service Variables show that some traders are not polite with buyers. However, in general business competition, traders continue to adjust prices to maintain sales volume, exacerbating market imbalances.

The results of Ervin's research (2022) entitled "Analysis of Business Competition of Basic Food Traders on Income in Pasar Semarang Baru, Pasir Sakti District" are in line with these findings. According to "Viewed from the Perspective of Islamic Business Ethics", business competition in the grocery market includes things like price, service, and location. In addition, the research he conducted found that there was unhealthy competition, especially in terms of price, where some traders raised prices excessively, which destabilized monthly income.

This is certainly contrary to Islamic business ethics that emphasize honesty, fairness, and blessings in business. Therefore, this study confirms that improvements in service aspects, proper product selection, and strategic location arrangement are essential to create healthy competition in the market. To create a

fair and competitive business environment in Sinakma Market, it is necessary to implement market regulations and trader coaching.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and data analysis regarding the influence of the variables of Product, Price, Place, and Service on Business Competition for Tobacco Traders in Sinakma Market, it can be concluded as follows:

- a. **The Regression Model is Feasible to Use:** The data used in this study have met the classical assumption test, namely the normality test shows that the data is normally distributed, and the multicollinearity test shows that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity between the independent variables;
- b. **Simultaneous Effect of Independent Variables:** Based on the F test, all independent variables (Product, Price, Place, and Service) simultaneously have a significant effect on the level of business competition of basic food traders. This indicates that the four variables together determine the variation of business competition in the market;
- c. **Partial Effect of Free Variables:** The t-test shows that only the Service variable has a significant effect on Business Competition partially, with the largest contribution of influence. Meanwhile, the variables of Product, Price, and Place do not show a significant effect individually;
- d. **Model Strength Level (Adjusted R²):** The adjusted R square value of 0.099 or 9.9% indicates that variations in business competition can only be explained by 9.9% by the variables of Product, Price, Place, and Service. The remaining 90.1% is influenced by other factors outside the model that need to be studied further in future research;
- e. **Field Findings and Competition Context:** Direct observation shows that the form of competition that occurs between traders in Sinakma Market tends to be unhealthy. This can be seen from the practice of price slashing, product mismatches with consumer needs, less strategic locations, and less friendly services. This condition has an impact on market imbalance and a decline in the quality of competition in general; and
- f. **Relevance to Previous Research:** The results of this study support the findings of Ervin (2022), who asserted that unfair competition in terms of price and service has a negative impact on income stability and violates the principles of business ethics, especially in an Islamic perspective.

2. SUGGESTION

To create healthy and consistent competition in Sinakma Market in Jayawijaya Regency, it is necessary to:

- a. Improved customer service from traders;
- b. Product selection based on customer needs;
- c. Rearrangement of business locations in a more thoughtful manner; and

- d. Supervision and training from the government or market managers to encourage fair and ethical competitive practices.

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